

Data Management Plan

Veteran tapes - Sara Poggio

Contact person: *There is no contact person specified yet*

Based on: *Common DSW Knowledge Model, 2.4.4 (dsw:root:2.4.4)*

Project phase: *Before Submitting the Proposal*

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Data Management Plan created in Data Stewardship Wizard «ds-wizard.org»

Projects

We will be working on the following projects and for those are the data and work described in this DMP.

There are no projects described for this DMP.

Section A: Data Collection

1. What data will you collect or create?

Non-equipment datasets

We also collect data from questionnaires and case report forms.

Data formats and types

We will be using the following data formats and types:

- [FAIR Implementation Profile Ontology](#)

It is not a standardized format because there is no standardized format for this data type. This is a suitable format for long-term archiving. We will have only a small amount of data stored in this format.

2. How will the data be collected or created?

There will be no instrument dataset in this project.

Data storage and file conventions

We will use a filesystem with files and folders with the following folder conventions:

- There will be a **folder for each sample/subject**.
- There will be a **(sub)folder for each (repeated) analysis**.
- There will be a **(sub)folder for each step in the analysis workflow**.

We will be storing data in an "object store" system.

We will use a relational database system to store project data. Modifications will be made by *Expiring* the existing data and *Adding* updated data.

Section B: Documentation and Meta-data

3. What documentation and meta-data will accompany the data?

List of data to be published is given in Section E, Question 9. This also includes information about catalogs where the data can be found. Information about data

types used is given in Section A, Question 1.

We will use lab notebooks to make sure that there is good provenance of the data analysis.

We will be documenting the data with Dublin Core, DataCite, and DDI (Data Documentation Initiative) metadata standards. The provenance will be captured using W3C PROV.

Section C: Ethics and Legal Compliance

4. How will you manage any ethical issues?

5. How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

We will be working with the philosophy *as open as possible* for our data.

All of our data can become completely open immediately.

Data that is not legally restrained will be released after a fixed time period (3 months), unconditionally.

Our data is legally not copyrightable, there is no legal owner.

Section D: Storage and Backup

6. How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Storage needs are small at the beginning and will grow later.

All essential data is also stored elsewhere to prevent a total loss of data. We will make (automated) backups of all data stored outside of the working area.

7. How will you manage access and security?

Project members will not store data or software on computers in the lab or external hard drives connected to those computers. They will not carry data with them (e.g. on laptops, USB sticks, or other external media). All data centers where

project data is stored carry sufficient certifications. All project web services are addressed via secure HTTP (https://...). Project members have been instructed about both generic and specific risks to the project.

The risk of information loss in the project or organization is acceptably low. The risk of information leak in the project or organization is acceptably low. The possible impact to the project or organization if information is vandalised is small.

All personal data will be collected anonymously.

Anyone in the institute can read data, only project members can request write access.

Section E: Selection and Preservation

8. Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

9. What is the longterm preservation plan for the dataset?

The costs related to the used repositories will be carried by (one of) the institutes involved in the project.

We have a reserved budget for the time and effort it will take to prepare the data for publication.

Section F: Data Sharing

10. How will you share the data?

Information about used repositories (i.e. where will potential users find out about the data) is provided in Section E, Question 9.

Embargo on the data is described in Section C, Question 5, and Section F, Question 11.

11. Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Ethical and legal restrictions are documented under Section C. We have used the Data Stewardship Wizard, which made us aware of options to minimize the restrictions.

No data sharing agreement will be required.

Section G: Responsibilities and Resources

12. Who will be responsible for data management?

Sara Poggio is responsible for implementing the DMP, and ensuring it is reviewed and revised.

Sara Poggio is responsible for the management and proficiency of data including data processing, data policies, data guidelines, and data availability.

13. What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

To execute the DMP, no additional specialist expertise is required.

Charges applied by data repositories (if any) are mentioned already in Section E, Question 9.